

PREVALENCE OF HEPATITIS C VIRUS AMONG HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS IN SANA'A HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: The hepatitis C virus (HCV) is highly infection prevalent among patients undergoing hemodialysis (HD) and constitutes the major threat that challenges the health system in developing countries. The main objective: is to find out the prevalence rate of HCV infection and risk factors among patients attending the dialysis centers in AL-Thawrah General Hospital and AL-Gumhuri Teaching Hospital in Sana'a city, Yemen. Method: A cross-sectional assessment of hemodialysis patients. Three hundred and eighty-four (384) serum specimens were collected from HD patients from 4th February 2023 to 7th February 2023. Also, the data concerning risk factors were collected by using a designed questionnaire. The collected specimens were screened for HCV antibodies by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) techniques. Results: the overall prevalence of HCV, was (21.4%) recorded in this study.

The highest infection was reported in AL-Thawrah General Hospital, and generally the highest infection was reported in patients aged >40 years ($P=0.05$), females 25% ($P=0.04$), non-educated 24.7%, single 26.4%, urban 21.9%, duration of dialysis >one year 26.9% ($P=0.01$), have no history of surgery 22.4%, blood transfusion 25.1% ($P=0.01$), and those attending multicenter 26.9% ($P=0.03$). It can be concluded that the high prevalence of hepatitis infections among HD patients in Yemen represents a serious community health problem to become a nosocomial infection in dialysis units. So, strict adherence to proper and effective procedures for infection control may be reduced and prevented the prevalence of hepatitis infections. **Conclusion:** HCV is very common infection in hemodialysis patients

and prevalence of infection is high in those patients compared to general population, prevalence rate of HCV infection varies between different hemodialysis centers; the highest prevalence rate of HCV infection was found in AL-Thawrah General Hospital, while the low prevalence rate was found in AL-Gumhouri Teaching Hospital, risk factors contributing to high HCV infection rates include (Age, Sex, duration of dialysis, blood transfusion and attending multi dialysis center), and there is no statistical significant association between HCV infection and risk factor include (education status, Residence, Marital status and History of surgery) in Sana'a city, Yemen.

KEYWORDS: Hepatitis C, Hemodialysis, Risk factors, Sana'a city-Yemen.

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection is a major concern for the public health worldwide in both developing and developed countries (Simmonds *et al.*, 1993). Transmission of HCV infection is mainly by exposure to infected devices and tools despite rigid hygienic control, infected blood or blood products, hemodialysis, intravenous (IV) drug abuse and organ transplantation (Alavian *et al.*, 2008). The estimation of national prevalence and ways of transmission of HCV should be completed in order to allow the national authorities to prioritize preventive measures and have the best and most appropriate use of available resources. Epidemiological surveys on the roles of potential risk factors, such as injections for medications, vaccinations, medical procedures, tattooing and injections outside of medical settings, have shown a wide geographical variation with major implications for the populations and potential management, prevention and control plans (Smith *et al.*, 1995; Lavanchy *et al.*, 2011). Prospective investigations have revealed that about 80% of the acute hepatitis C cases progress to chronic infection; about 10%-20% of these cases will develop chronic liver disease complications, like liver cirrhosis, within two to three decades of onset and about 1%-5% will end up with liver cancer (Lavanchy *et al.*, 2011; Lavanchy *et al.*, 2009).

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection is a major problem affecting about 184 million people worldwide, or roughly 3% of the world's population is currently infected (Hadigan and Kottlil, 2011). While most countries have prevalence rates ranging from 1 to 2%, there are some countries with relatively high prevalence rates, including Egypt (15%), Pakistan (4.7%) and Taiwan (4.4%) (Sievert *et al.*, 2011). HCV prevalence in the Hemodialysis patients in Yemen was estimated to be 1.8% (Chaabna *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, in 2019 the prevalence

of HCV in the Hemodialysis patients in Yemen was estimated to be 10.7% (Hanash SH *et al*, 2019)

No comprehensive report was presented, particularly during the last 3 years, in order to give a sight about the prevalence of HCV infection among hemodialysis patients in Sana'a city-Yemen. It was founded that evaluation and estimation of the prevalence in this country and performing comparisons among them may help researchers and health policy makers create or modify research projects, preventive programs and management plans for the hemodialysis patients in the region. There is a clear relationship between infection with hepatitis C virus and patients with kidney failure, so patients undergoing hemodialysis are more likely to be infected with Hepatitis (Jalil, M.B *et al*, 2022).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design and study area. This study was a cross sectional study in Al-Thawra General hospital and Al-Gumhouri Teaching hospital in Sana'a city, Yemen.

Study Population

Inclusion criteria. The target population was renal failure patients undergoing hemodialysis of both sexes and all ages.

Exclusion criteria. Renal failure patients undergoing hemodialysis that has positive HIV and HBV are rejected.

Sample size: The sample was 384 which collected from hemodialysis patients.

Data collection: The data was collected by using predesigned questionnaire which include personal information, health state and researcher questions (Appendix 1).

Blood collection: Approximately 5 ml of blood drawn from each patient before dialysis then put in gel tube without anticoagulant then waited 15-30 minutes event for clotting and serum obtained by using centrifugation at 3500 rounds per minute for 5 minutes. The serum put in Eppendorf tubes and preserved at -20 °C until used.

Detection of HCV: Anti-HCV test was performed by Manual ELISA method to detect the presence of antibody in serum directed against HCV in National Central of Public Health Laboratories Center using (InTec Diagnostic, China).

Principle. In this assay, Human serum or plasma is diluted in a specimen diluent and incubated with a microtiter well coated with recombinant HCV antigen. During the course of the first incubation any anti-HCV antibodies in the sample will bind to the immobilized antigen. Following washing to remove unbound material, the captured anti-HCV antibodies are incubated with horseradish peroxidase conjugated monoclonal anti-human IgG. During the course of second incubation the conjugated will bind to antibody immobilized in the first step. After removal of excess conjugate, bound enzyme is detected by the addition of a solution containing tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) and hydrogen peroxidase. A purple color will develop in the wells which contained anti-HCV positive samples. The enzyme reaction is terminated by addition of sulphuric acid. The intensity of color developed is read spectrophotometrically at 450nm.

Procedure

1. Bring all reagents and Specimens to room temperature (18-25 °C) for the assay.
2. Prepare the needed number of wells, including one well for blank, two wells for negative control, two wells for positive control, and one well for each specimen.
3. Add 100 µL specimen diluent to each well.
4. Add 10 µL specimen, negative control and positive control to each appropriate well according to data sheet.
5. Tap the plate to mix.
6. Incubate the plate in a 37 °C for 60 minutes
7. wash each well 5 times with wash buffer by wash procedure.
8. Add 100 µL Enzyme conjugate working solution to each well.
9. Incubate the plate in a 37 °C for 30 minutes.
10. Wash each well times with wash buffer by wash procedure.
11. Add 50 µL Color A and 50 µL Color B to each well in order, tap the plate to mix.
12. incubate the plate in a 37 °C for 30 minutes.
13. Stop the reaction by adding 50 µL Stopping Solution to each well, tap the plate to mix.
14. Read the absorbance of solution in each well at 450nm

Statistical analysis

The data was entered into the computer to the statistical package for social studies International Business Machine Statistical Package for social studies IBM SPSS version 26 will be presented as frequencies, percentage, tabulation or graphical representation required

used for analysis. The statistical significance of associations between such variables were tested using Pearson's chi-square or Fisher's exact tests, which ever appropriate. Bivariate logistic regression model was developed for the identification of the, possible risk factors where odds ratios (ORs) and their corresponding 95.0% confidence intervals (CIs) were reported. All statistical analysis will be performed using the IBM SPSS version 26, 2019 data with P-value <0.05 will be statistically significant.

Ethical Consideration. Contents was taken from all patients and they were informed that patients are voluntary and that they can refuse this without stating any reason.

RESULTS

Characteristics of Hemodialysis Patients included in the study

Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to sex

The frequency of females was higher (204/384) 53.1. % compared to males (180/384) was 46.9% among Hemodialysis Patients in Sana'a city, Yemen (Figure 2).

Figure (2) Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to sex in Sana'a city, Yemen.

Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to educational status

The frequency of non- educated (190/384) 49.5% was lower compared to educated was (194/384) 50.5%. (Figure 3).

Figure (3) Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to educational level in Sana'a city, Yemen.

Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to residence

The frequency was higher among Hemodialysis Patients from urban areas (302/384) 78.6% compared to rural area (82/384) 21.4% among Hemodialysis Patients (Figure 4).

Figure (4) Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to Residence in Sana'a city, Yemen.

Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to age

The frequency of less or equal than 40 years old patients (162/384) 42.2% was lower compared to more than 40 years old patients was (222/384) 57.8%. (Figure 5).

Figure (5) Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to age in Sana'a city, Yemen.

Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to marital status

The frequency of single patients (53/384) 13.8% was lower compared to married patients was (331/384) 86.2%. (Figure 6).

Figure (6) Distribution of Hemodialysis Patients according to marital in Sana'a city, Yemen.

3.2.1 Seroprevalence of HCV antibodies among Hemodialysis Patients

The seroprevalence of Anti-HCV among Hemodialysis Patients in Sana'a city, Yemen were (82/384) 21.4% (95% CI: 17.6%-25.5%). (Figure7).

Figure (7) Seroprevalence of anti-HCV among Hemodialysis patients in Sana'a city, Yemen.

Seroprevalence of HCV antibodies among Hemodialysis Patients according to Hemodialysis center in Sana'a city, Yemen

The seroprevalence of Anti-HCV among Hemodialysis Patients in AL-Thawra hospital were (57/200) 28.5%, while Al-Jomhour Hospital were (25/184) 13.6%.

The highest prevalence rate of HCV infection was found in AL-Thawra hospital.

Table 1: Seroprevalence of HCV antibodies according to Hemodialysis center.

Hemodialysis center	N	n (%)
AL-Thawra hospital	200	57(28.5)
Al-Gomhour Hospital	184	25(13.6)

Socio- demographic factors associated with *HCV* seropositivity

The Socio demographic risk factors were included age, sex; educational status, marital status, and residence area are summarized in **Table 2**. The seroprevalence of anti *HCV* antibodies was significantly associated with age groups who are more than 40 were 58 (26.1%), more affected than less than or equal 40 were 24 (14.8%) (OR, 2.03; 95% CI, 1.20-3.44; $P= 0.05$). The female patients were 51 (25%), more affected than male 31 (17.2%) and it was factor to *HCV* was significantly associated (OR, 1.63;95% CI, 1.2-2.64; $P = 0.04$).

Univariable analysis showed that not significant between *HCV* antibodies with marital status who was married 68 (20.5%) higher than single was 14 (26.4%) (OR, 0.72; 95% CI, 0.37-1.40; $P = 0.21$).

The seroprevalence of *HCV* antibodies in urban areas were more affected 66 (21.9%) than rural 16 (19.5%) without statistically significant association (OR, 0.87; 95% CI, 0.47-1.60; $P = 0.39$). Also, non-educated patients were more affected 47 (24.7%) than educated patients 35 (18%) with not statistically associated (OR, 1.49; 95% CI, 0.91-2.44; $P = 0.07$). **Table 2** Socio- demographic factors associated with *HCV* seropositivity.

*Significant association ($P \leq 0.05$). N; the number of Hemodialysis patients examined, n; the number of seropositive patients, OR; odds ratio, CI; confidence interval.

Association between health risk factors with *HCV* seropositivity

The association between health risk factors of Hemodialysis patients related with *HCV* antibodies represented in **Table 3**. Hemodialysis patients who are dialysis more than one year 80 (26.9%), more affected than Hemodialysis patients who are dialysis for less or equal than one year 2 (2.3%). in this result find a statistically significant association (OR, 15.67; 95% CI, 3.77-65.17; $P= 0.01$). A statistically significant was showed between the seroprevalence of Anti-*HCV* antibody among Hemodialysis patients who was receive blood transfusion 78 (25.1%), and Hemodialysis patients who was not receive blood transfusion 4 (5.5%), (OR, 5.76; 95% CI, 2.04-16.34; $P = 0.01$). The Hemodialysis patients who reported to attending multi dialysis center were 39 (26.9%), compared to those who reported to attending single dialysis center 43 (18%), in this result find statistically significant association (OR, 1.68; 95% CI, 1.03-2.75; $P = 0.03$) with anti-*HCV*.

The seroprevalence of Anti-HCV antibody among Hemodialysis patients who have not history of surgery is more 55 (22.4%) than who have history of surgery 27 (19.4 %) and find a no statistically significant difference (OR, 0.83; 95% CI, 0.40-1.30; P= 0.29).

Table 2: Socio- demographic factors associated with HCV seropositivity.

Variable	N	n (%)	OR (95%CI)	P value
Duration of dialysis				
≤ One year	87	2(2.3)	Reference	
> One year	297	80(26.9)	15.67 (3.77-65.17)	0.01*
History of surgery				
Yes	139	27(19.4)	Reference	
No	245	55(22.4)	0.83(0.40-1.30)	0.29
Receive BT				
Yes	311	78(25.1)	Reference	
No	73	4(5.5)	5.76(2.04-16.34)	0.01*
Attending multi dialysis center				
Yes	145	39(26.9)	Reference	
No	239	43(18)	1.68(1.03-2.75)	0.03*

DISCUSSION

Hepatitis C virus is a bloodborne virus and the most common modes of infection are through unsafe injection practices, inadequate sterilization of medical equipment such as dialysis machine (Baghza *et al.*, 2014). The prevalence of anti-HCV among hemodialysis patients suggesting that dialysis patients may be at higher risk of acquiring HCV infection (Abdulwahab *et al.*, 2021). Patients treated in hemodialysis units with high prevalence of HCV infection are at increased risk of acquiring infection. However, there is a considerable variation in the rate of HCV infection in hemodialysis units worldwide and difference within the same country (Rockey *et al.*, 2009).

In our study the overall prevalence of HCV among hemodialysis patients in Yemen was 21.4 %, this rate is very much higher than the rate reported by a previous study, in 2019 in Yemen, which reported 10.7% (Hanash SH *et al.*, 2019).

Prevalence of HCV infection in general population in Yemen was 2.5 % (Ahmed *et al.*, 2021). Difference in prevalence rate of HCV infection between hemodialysis patient and general population, indicating the high risk for infectivity of hepatitis virus in hemodialysis center (Strader *et al.*, 2004; Alashek *et al.*, 2012).

By comparing the prevalence rate of this current study with other countries the prevalence of anti-HCV revealed in this study was 21.4 %. This result is lower than that reported by

previous studies in Egypt (2020) was 34%, (Abde Wahed *et al*, 2020). (Madhavan *et al*, 2020) who these reported the seroprevalence of anti-HCV in south India was lower than from this study were 8%.

The current study showed that the rate of anti-HCV in Hemodialysis patients was 21.4%. This result is similar to the previous studies done among.

Hemodialysis patients that reported by (Abdulwahab *et al*, 2021) who recorded 20 % in Iraq. In this current study there has been wide variation in prevalence rate of HCV observed between different hemodialysis units in Sana'a city-Yemen, ranging 28.5% in AL-Thawra General Hospital to 13.6% in Al-Gumhouri Teaching Hospital.

Difference in prevalence rate of HCV infection between hemodialysis centers may be due to different applications of disinfection and precaution taken by staff and patients in hemodialysis centers. As well as the effect of nosocomial infection transmission of HCV as indicated by epidemiological and molecular studies have showed the role of hemodialysis environment for dissemination of HCV between patients (Fabrizi *et al*, 2002; Somi *et al*, 2008). Also, in this study it is not unusual to find staff taking care of susceptible and infected patients in the same shift, and also they didn't routinely discard gloves after use (WHO, 1999; Samimi *et al*, 2012). The low prevalence of HCV infection in some hemodialysis centers may be due to partial immunosuppression in those patients resulting in a poor antibody response to hepatitis virus infection, making serology screening of HCV underestimated so they will be on seronegative machines spreading infectivity to seronegative patients (Ghany *et al*, 1998; Strader *et al*, 2004).

In our study, prevalence of HCV infection showed statistically significant association with patient age, elderly patients were at higher risk for HCV infection, ($P = 0.05$) this agree with the previous study carried, in 2020 in tertiary care hospital in India were the rate of infection among elderly patients was higher compared with younger patients (Madhavan *et al*, 2020). In the current study, prevalence of HCV infection showed statistically significant association with patient sex, female patients were at higher risk for HCV infection, ($P = 0.04$) this disagree with the previous study carried, in (2020).

in south india tertiary care hospital were the rate of infection among female was 3%, compared to 5% in males (Madhavan *et al*, 2020).

A positive significant relationship had been found in this study between patients who attending multicenter and risk of infection compare with patients who are on single center dialysis, ($P = 0.03$) this agrees with studies conducted in Iraq that showed effect of attending multicenter on seroconversion rate of HCV infection (Abdulwahab *et al.*, 2021), This might be related to different degree of cleaning and disinfection of hemodialysis membranes, machines equipment and environmental surface to prevent nosocomial transmission (Kashem *et al.*, 2003).

In the current study, the prevalence rate of HCV infection demonstrated a statistically significant in relation to the length of time of hemodialysis the patients spend, ($P = 0.01$) this finding in agreement with many studies conducted in Iraq and India (Abdulwahab *et al.*, 2021; Madhavan *et al.*, 2020), which concluded that dialysis treatment could be a specific and independent risk factor for HCV infection. This may be related to the increase of period of exposure to the virus, the more the patients stay in contact with hemodialysis machines, the more the risk to HCV infection increase (Alashek *et al.*, 2012). As well as hemodialysis patients are immunocompromised and any minor breach in universal control of HCV infection could make them exposed to the virus (Kashem *et al.*, 2003).

In this study, blood transfusion considered an important factor in the transmission of HCV Infection, ($P = 0.01$), this agrees with studies conducted in Iraq (Abdulwahab *et al.*, 2021).

In this study, patients living in the urban area had the highest infections with HCV (21.9%) compared to the rural area (19.5%) and there was no statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). Our result agreed with other study reported by (Almezgagi *et al.*, 2020) who not found association between anti-HCV and residence.

The prevalence of HCV infection in the present study were remarkably higher among non-educated patients than other patients who are educated. However, there was no statistically significant relationship between HCV infection and the education status of the patients, ($P = 0.07$). The different result recorded by (Almezgagi *et al.*, 2020) in Ibb City-Yemen.

The results regarding marital status showed that the high infection with HCV was among unmarried compared with married HD patients with of 26.4% and 20.5%, respectively without statistically significant, ($P > 0.05$). This result was similar to that obtained by (Almezgagi *et al.*, 2020).

In this study, no statistically significant association between anti-HCV and history of surgical procedure ($P = 0.29$). In this result there was an agreement to that reported by (Almezgagi *et al.*, 2020) among HD patients in Ibb City-Yemen.

Finally, this study intends to be the gateway of many researchers to look into this subject and for policy makers to implement good public health strategies to tackle this growing public health issue.

One of our study limitations is the absence of data of HCV testing at the molecular level because there may be cases of hidden HCV that could not be detected through the ELISA test.

CONCLUSION

HCV is very common infection in hemodialysis patients and Prevalence of infection is high in those patients compared to general population. Prevalence rate of HCV infection varies between different hemodialysis centers; the highest prevalence rate of HCV infection was found in AL-Thawra General Hospital 28.5 %, while the low prevalence rate was found in Al Gumhouri Teaching Hospital 13.6%. Risk factors contributing to high HCV infection rates include (Age, Sex, and duration of dialysis, blood transfusion and attending multi dialysis center). There is no statistically significant association between HCV infection and risk factor include (education status, Residence, Marital status and History of surgery) in Sana'a city, Yemen.

REFERENCES

1. Abdulwahab, H., Al-Juboori, R., Hamad, R., Taqi, M., Mahaan, J., Mushtaq, T. and Abd. (2021). Seroprevalence of Hepatitis B and C Virus and Associated Risk Factors in Hemodialysis Units in Al-Anbar Province.
2. Abdulwahed, H. and Mostafa, N. (2020). Prevalence and seroconversion of hepatitis C among hemodialysis patients in Assiut governorate, Egypt. 32(1).
3. Alashek, W.A., McIntyre, C.W., Taal, W.M.(2012). Hepatitis B and C infection in Hemodialysis patients in Libya: prevalence, incidence and risk factors. BMC Infectious Diseases, 12: 265.
4. Alavian, S.M., Hajarizadeh, B., Ahmadzad-Asl, M., Kabir, A., Bagheri-Lankarani K.(2008). Hepatitis B Virus infection in Iran: A systematic review. Hapat Mon.; 8: 281–294.

5. Almezgagi, M.M., Edrees, W.H., Al-Shehari, W.A., Al-Moyed, K., Al-Khwilany, R.S. and Abbas, A.B. (2020). Prevalence of Hepatitis B Virus and Hepatitis C Virus and Associated Risk Factors among Hemodialysis Patients in Ibb City-Yemen. *PSM Microbiology*, [online] 5(2): 32–40.
6. Baghza, N.M. (2014). The Prevalence of Hepatitis C Virus among Hemodialysis Patients in Yemen. *Journal of Purity, Utility Reaction and Environment*.
7. Fabrizi, F., Poordad, F.F., Martin, P. (2002) Hepatitis C infection and the patient with end-stage renal disease. *Hepatology*, 36: 3-10.
8. Ghany, M., Strader, B., Thomas, L.(1998). Diagnosis, management, and treatment of hepatitis C: An update. *Hepatology*, 49: 1335–1374.
9. Hadigan, C. and Kottlil, S. (2011). Hepatitis C virus infection and coinfection with human immunodeficiency virus: challenges and advancements in management. *Jama*, 306(3): 294-301.
10. Hanash, S.H., Al-Shamahy H.A., Bamshmous, M.H.S.(2019). Prevalence and genotyping of hepatitis C virus in hemodialysis patients and evaluation of HCV-core antigen test in screening patients for dialysis in Sana'a city, Yemen. *Universal Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 4(2): 14-18.
11. Jalil, M.B., ALnabi, D.I.B.A. and Shaker, M.N. (2022). The Seroprevalence of Hepatitis C virus infection among Renal failure patients as a risk factor in hemodialysis units in Basrah - Iraq. *Al-Kunooze Scientific Journal*.
12. Kashem, A., Nusairat, I., Mohamad, M. (2003) Hepatitis C Virus among Hemodialysis Patients in Najran: Prevalence is More Among Multi-Center Visitors. *Saudi J Kidney Dis Transpl*, 14: 206-11.
13. Lavanchy, D. (2011). Evolving epidemiology of hepatitis C virus. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 17(2): 107-115.
14. Lavanchy D. (2009). The global burden of hepatitis C. *Liver Int.*, 29 Suppl 1: 74–81.
15. Madhavan, A., Sachu, A., Balakrishnan, A.K., Vasudevan, A., Balakrishnan, S. and Vasudevapanicker, J. (2020). Prevalence of hepatitis C among haemodialysis patients in a tertiary care hospital in South India.
16. Samimi, K.R., Hosseini, M., Mobeini, G.(2012) Hepatitis C virus infection among multitransfused patients and personnel in hemodialysis units in central Islamic Republic of Iran *EMHJ.*, 18(3).
17. Sievert, W., Altraif, I., Razavi, H.A., Abdo, A., Ahmed, E.A., AlOmair, A., Amarapurkar, D., Chen, C.H., Dou, X., El Khayat, H. and Elshazly, M. (2011). A systematic review of

- hepatitis C virus epidemiology in Asia, Australia and Egypt. *Liver International*, 31(s2): 61-80.
18. Simmonds, P., Holmes, E.C., Cha, T.A., Chan., S.W., McOmish, F., Irvine, B., Beall. E., Yap, P.L, Kolberg, J., Urdea, M.S.(1993). Classification of hepatitis C virus into six major genotypes and a series of subtypes by phylogenetic analysis of the NS-5 region. *J Gen Viral*. 74(Pt 11): 2391–2399.
 19. Smith, D.B., Mellor, J., Jarvis, L.M, Davidson, F., Kolberg, J., Urdea, M., Yap, P.L., Simmonds, P.(1995). Variation of the hepatitis C virus 5' non-coding region: implications for secondary structure, virus detection and typing. The International HCV Collaborative Study Group. *J Gen Viral*, 76(Pt 7): 1749–1761.
 20. Strader, D.B., Wright, T., Thomas, D.L. (2004). Diagnosis, management, and treatment of hepatitis C. *Hepatology*, 39: 1147-71.
 21. WHO: Global surveillance and control of hepatitis C. Report of a WHO consultation organized in collaboration with the viral hepatitis prevention board, antwerp, belgium. *J Viral Hepat*, 1999; 6(1): 35-47.